

Booklet of Participants

Paola from Spain

¡Hola a todos! Passionate advocate for life and the world. Originally from Guatemala and Ecuador, I've been living in Spain for over four years. I firmly believe in entrepreneurship as a powerful and capable force to change the world. It has the potential to drive innovation, create opportunities, and address global challenges. Thank you for being part of this program and for inspiring positive change and innovation every day!

Vanesa from Slovakia

Ahojte všetci! Coming from Slovakia, a country known for its stunning landscapes and deep-rooted traditions, I am thrilled to be part of this dynamic community. The spirit of Slovak ingenuity and resilience has been a guiding force in my entrepreneurial journey. Our program has shown me the power of collaboration and the importance of preserving cultural integrity while embracing innovation.

Bianca from Italy

Ciao a tutti e tutte! Coming from Italy, a land of artistic greatness and culinary excellence, I have always been surrounded by creativity and passion. After spending several years studying and working abroad, I decided to return to my country to explore and support innovative ideas that could solve Italy's problems and promote our culture.

Anete from Latvia

Sveiki! As a native of Latvia, I am immensely proud to contribute to Riga's vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem. Latvia's deep connection to nature and its innovative spirit have been a source of inspiration throughout my journey. I am grateful for the opportunity to collaborate with such a diverse group of entrepreneurs and to witness firsthand how our unique cultural backgrounds enrich our collective creativity.

Together, we have embarked on a journey of growth, learning, and innovation. This booklet serves as a testament to the hard work and dedication of all the entrepreneurs who have participated in this program. We hope it inspires you as much as it has inspired us. Thank you for joining us in celebrating the future of entrepreneurship.

Warm regards,
The Incubation Team

Message from the Incubation Team

Paola

Vanesa

Bianca

Anete

Meet our cohorts!

Córdoba

ASIS

ABOUT THE PROJECT

A digital application designed to meet the needs of the elderly and other groups, bridging gaps where public or private services may not reach. Our service offers personalized, quality assistance and is continually evolving through the application of new technologies. Our target clients include elderly people and their relatives, as well as other groups with specific needs, such as individuals with different abilities. Public administrations are also key clients, although in a more indirect manner. We aim to be their versatile solution, offering them the opportunity to optimize their services by improving their management both economically and operationally.

FOUNDER Juan Antonio Sánchez Parra

“I have improved my skills in creative thinking and digital marketing and hope to develop knowledge in other areas, such as data analytics.”

Listen&Speak, Skills for Nursery School Teachers

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Listen&Speak, Skills for Nursery School Teachers seeks to empower individuals in the early childhood education sector, primarily women, as key players in the initial English language learning process for infants. The project aims to democratize the knowledge and functional management of language skills, making the acquisition of early competencies accessible to both young learners and teachers. We strive for real skills, not empty certificates, enabling young children to lay the foundations for bilingualism.

FOUNDER **Cristina Rentería Garita**

“Through mentorship, I've honed my financial projection skills, while simultaneously delving into the intricacies of business management, where every decision becomes a strategic move toward profitability, efficiency, and sustainability.”

Síntesis Cibernética de Plantas S.L.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Síntesis Cibernética de Plantas S.L., known commercially as SCP, is a startup established in Barcelona in 2023. Our vision is to spearhead the integration of agriculture, ecology, and data technology through our platform specializing in the analysis and modeling of plant species data, as well as the processing of vegetation images, particularly those captured by drones. SCP specializes in providing technology and data analysis services to the agricultural sector, with a primary focus on precision agriculture.

FOUNDER **Gustavo Giudici**

“The program has significantly boosted my confidence in our business. Through extensive discussions and refinement of every aspect, it has prompted thorough consideration of our communication strategies with customers, development of our sales model, identification of core customer demographics, and much more.”

Lector

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Our goal is to launch a mobile application that offers short, high quality texts for those who love reading in daily cycles. Users will be able to save and share these texts, fostering a community dedicated to cultivating the habit of reading, improving concentration and increasing retention of texts that make a difference in each reader's personality. Initially, the application will focus on providing varied content and basic saving and sharing functionalities, creating an interactive and shared reading experience. Later, we will expand with a subscription plan that will include advanced functionalities, such as a citation manager and personalized recommendations. In the long term, we will develop a marketplace where new authors and publishers will be able to publish and sell their works, diversifying the digital literary landscape. This approach will allow us to generate revenue through subscriptions and sales commissions, positioning our application as an essential tool for reading in the digital age.

FOUNDERS José Bomfim Fábio San Juan

“We have come a long way in understanding the market and calculating financial projections. We now know how to plan better, identify our customers and figure out how to build a service that people are willing to pay for. We have also better evaluated marketing strategies and are more inclined to use inbound marketing strategies rather than funnel acquisition.”

CREAteatro

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The goal is to establish a comprehensive center for performing arts aimed at enhancing the social integration of individuals with mental health challenges, utilizing theater as a therapeutic medium. Through workshops and introductory courses in theatrical interpretation, we aim to provide a platform for creative and therapeutic expression, fostering integration between individuals with and without mental disorders. This approach seeks to highlight the value of individuals facing mental health issues while promoting personal growth through theater as a means of introspection. Additionally, it aims to develop and enhance both non-verbal and verbal communication skills, facilitating self-awareness and fostering personal and professional empowerment.

FOUNDER **Ángel Alonso Rodríguez**

"I've developed significant hard skills, particularly in social media marketing and financial planning. Additionally, I've adopted fresh perspectives on executing an initial project, allowing me to effectively shape my original idea."

Hunter Health

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Hunter Health presents a mental fitness ecosystem dedicated to addressing the mental health epidemic by improving accessibility to resources. We've developed a robust mental wellness ecosystem, offering individuals and companies seamless access to vital mental health services, tools, and educational resources. Our platform is designed to revolutionize mental healthcare by providing personalized, stigma-free support. With a single solution that connects users to therapy, resources, and communities, we're poised to make a significant impact on individuals' mental health journeys while addressing the broader societal need for accessible mental wellness solutions.

FOUNDER Virginia Pérez Nieto

“When I started the program, I had a vision and a passion for creating a company that would make an impact in the world. This program provided me with the tools, mentorship, and community necessary to navigate the complexities of entrepreneurship and bring my ideas to life.”

BWell Lab

ABOUT THE PROJECT

BWell Lab is a well-being laboratory dedicated to supporting individuals in their personal development and organizations in achieving holistic well-being. The organization designs meaningful spaces for learning, connection, and growth—both personally and professionally.

Comprising a team of 12 professionals from diverse disciplines, BWell Lab is committed to helping individuals and teams cultivate leadership skills, emotional intelligence, and overall well-being. Their collaborative approach empowers people and organizations with practical tools to pursue and achieve their goals.

With a strong focus on sustainable societal development, BWell Lab invites others to be part of the well-being revolution.

FOUNDER Tomás Nores

“The platform helped me a lot to structure my project and motivated me to professionalize my entrepreneurial journey. I highly recommend it! It's very detailed and gives you a comprehensive, 360-degree understanding of your project. It was challenging to go through because it makes you question many things—but it's absolutely worth it!”

A decorative graphic in the bottom right corner consisting of several yellow circles of varying sizes connected by thin yellow lines, resembling a network or molecular structure.

Arte y cultura en metal

ABOUT THE PROJECT

This project was born from the creativity of a couple who design and craft unique sculptural columns made from twisted iron—structures unlike anything else in the world. Using machinery invented and built by one of the founders, each piece is adorned with capitals, bases, and arches inspired by Andalusian culture. The sculptures are entirely original, made with natural elements and metals through artisanal processes. Their aim is to bring value and distinction to spaces while raising awareness around sustainability.

FOUNDER **Cristina Pedrajas**

"Before starting the In-Habit program, we knew nothing about the business world and relied purely on instinct. Now, we realize that there were things we were already doing well, but we've learned to organize our work more effectively. We now better understand our potential clients, our competitors, and the viability of our project through quantified financial projections. We've also defined our vision and mission."

"Thanks to this entrepreneurship program, we've regained our enthusiasm and have a clearer sense of our goals along with a roadmap to achieve them."

En la Tecla: Music for Everyone

ABOUT THE PROJECT

En la Tecla began with a simple belief: that music can be a powerful tool for social, emotional, and educational transformation. After years of training in music therapy and inclusion—and witnessing firsthand the challenges faced by neurodivergent families—I knew something needed to change.

That vision took form in En la Tecla: Music for Everyone, a project offering inclusive, professional, and accessible music therapy. With custom-made workshops and one-on-one sessions, I work closely with families, creating safe spaces and real community beyond the therapeutic setting.

FOUNDER **Ángela García Sánchez**

Participating in Bridge for Billions has been truly transformative—both personally and professionally. The program’s step-by-step approach helped me shape “En la Tecla: Music for Everyone” from an idea into a viable business model with a clear vision and solid strategy.

Bridge gave me clarity, tools, and—most importantly—confidence to pursue an inclusive, accessible, and sustainable path. I’m incredibly grateful for the experience.

Lucca

FOUNDERS Marina Barbati Alessio Guazzini

“The program provided us with new knowledge in setting up a business, even for our existing one. It guided us step by step, equipping us with the skills to follow all the important steps for realization in a linear and focused manner.”

info@dogphotoitaly.com

Dog Photo Italy

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Dog Photo Italy is the first Italian network dedicated to dog photography. Through photography, we celebrate the unique and special relationship between dogs and owners by creating tailor-made and tailored portraits. We automate all production processes, from booking to delivery of the printed photo.

FOUNDER **Michela Barbarese**

"I am happy to have participated and hope that this experience, which has enriched me both humanly and professionally, can be my stepping stone."

barbarese86@hotmail.com

GreenPaws Vet Laboratory

ABOUT THE PROJECT

GreenPaws was created to formulate safe cosmetic products and innovative, original complementary feeds from vegetable and food waste, all with a green and energy-saving perspective. Our products are consciously formulated to respect the dignity of animals. However, GreenPaws is more than just a product line; it is a broader initiative known as the GreenPaws Project. This project involves schools and associations through workshops and educational activities designed to teach young people and children about environmental and animal education and respect. We will dedicate a specific area within the company entirely to this project.

FOUNDERS

Sara Trivella
Micol GelliGiulia
VetroLisa Fagiolini

“The new soft skills I learned mainly concern negotiation and helped me hone my leadership skills. In terms of hard skills, the program helped me improve and refine project management, particularly financial planning.”

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Una Zampa per un Gesto

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The project idea operates on two fronts: it aims to assist children and young people with communication difficulties by utilizing various types of language, such as LIS (Italian Sign Language) or non-verbal communication, as approaches to socialization and the therapy of selective mutism. Additionally, it focuses on training dogs using the same communication methods, even for simple obedience commands. This approach promotes greater inclusion of these fragile groups in simple play contexts and ensures that dogs are well-trained for everyday life.

FOUNDER **Rebecca Milani**

“The program helped me prioritize tasks, develop financial planning skills, and identify my target audience, which includes groups, families, and individuals with pets.”

Instagram:
[@poderepoggiarello](#)

La volpe d'oro

ABOUT THE PROJECT

A multi-purpose facility of a social nature where various topics converge: tourism featuring local food and drink, dog education (with potential for an educational farm in the future), emphasizing intra- and inter-species socialization, and educational events suitable for all ages, with a special focus on children and the elderly. These events encompass health education, fostering respect for nature and its inhabitants, and offering sporting and musical activities.

FOUNDER **Francesca Innocenzi**

“This program has been instrumental in helping me develop a comprehensive financial projection plan and enhancing my skills in business plan development.”

info@farmavetpro.com

Farmavetpro

ABOUT THE PROJECT

A training academy for pharmacists, veterinarians, and other animal health professionals who aspire to launch their own projects, offering comprehensive support ranging from regulatory knowledge to digital communication skills.

FOUNDER **Ilaria Mati**

“This course helped me to learn how to better analyse the costs of my company. My mentor was fundamental, she understood my difficulties and helped me to deal with them. The whole team, first and foremost Bianca, was helpful and patient, true professionals.”

civuolefiutoprato@gmail.com

Ci vuole fiuto

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Ci vuole fiuto is, in addition to a dog training centre, a project with two objectives. The first is to help dog owners live their daily lives, with their four-legged friends, in a serene manner, especially when there are behavioural problems, through olfactory search. The second is to intervene in accommodation facilities to search for bedbugs, through detector dogs that I will train. The latter also aims to train staff for a new job.

FOUNDER **Airin Irene Superina**

“The good thing is that I have learnt to analyse”

airin.spr@gmail.com

EquiSfera

ABOUT THE PROJECT

In a unique setting, revaluing pastures and woods and a small lake in the heart of Tuscany, people and horses find their balance between environmental, economic and mental sustainability. Without straying into anachronisms or utopias, horses are bred and trained according to their inclinations in modern facilities with low environmental and landscape impact, boarded even if elderly, convalescent from sporting injuries or at the end of their careers, enjoying extensive pastures and woods. Patrons can benefit from a unique receptivity by sharing daily spaces with their horses, recreational or educational activities

Nitra

Aptet ISP, družstvo, r.s.p.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Integrative Social Enterprise - Supported Employment Agency. We address the training and employment of disadvantaged and vulnerable individuals in both open and sheltered labor markets. Our primary customers are companies facing labor shortages and willing to create suitable working conditions for people with specific needs.

FOUNDER **Stanislav Lorincz**

“The incubation program was extremely helpful in prompting the right questions and generating unbiased answers.”

lorincz@aptet.sk

VERDE

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Our vertical farm initiative offers a new perspective on our relationship with the environment and food production. By implementing vertical farming, we aim to bring sustainable, year-round healthy food production to cities, addressing some of today's biggest challenges. The main goal is to create a greener food system and healthier communities.

The design includes a lower section for business, coffee, and food, with an upper section dedicated to growing selected plants using vertical systems and hydroponics.

FOUNDER

Lucia Jasenovská

“The program was extremely beneficial and taught me everything I needed to know for successful entrepreneurship. I gained valuable knowledge in strategic planning, marketing, finance, and team management.”

lucia.jasenovska@gmail.com

Bikesharing Nitra

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Introducing our Community Bike Sharing program, a sustainable and convenient solution for urban mobility. Our model enhances community connectivity, reduces traffic congestion, and promotes a healthier lifestyle. Join us in revolutionizing the way we move around our cities!

FOUNDERS Jana Kuffová Popovicsová
Sandra Šubertová

“The Entrepreneur Incubation Program has been instrumental in helping us realize our visions and ideas.”

info@hidepark.sk

Vlna pod Tatrami

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Design, create and sell products made from local sheep wool and upcycled materials & organise training courses. My goal is to work mainly with Slovak sheep breeders and manufactures that process local sheep wool, thus addressing the whole production chain of products as locally as possible and with the smallest possible carbon footprint. At the same time, I also want to create with upcycled materials with reference to the practical "zero waste" life of our ancestors in order to reach modern people of the 21st century.

FOUNDER **Lívia Rášová**

"The program helped me to better understand business needs, define customer segments and optimize product size/weight."

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TOWMEOT

ABOUT THE PROJECT

TOWMEOT creates educational live concerts and artistic experiences for schools that help young people connect art, environment, and wellbeing in a way that feels real, fun, and memorable. Through music, storytelling, and interactive moments, we translate themes like nature protection, responsible everyday choices, and community values into an engaging experience that builds awareness, empathy, and creative confidence. By bringing culture directly into classrooms and local community spaces, we support the Art & Environment direction using art as a practical tool to strengthen inclusion, healthier habits, and a stronger relationship with the places we live in.

FOUNDER **Martin Dvornický**

“I left with a clearer roadmap, stronger planning habits, and more confidence to move from idea to delivery.”

towmeot@gmail.com

Beauty House

ABOUT THE PROJECT

My primary activity involves providing comprehensive services to women. I aim to offer a wide range of high-quality services under one roof, catering to all their needs and fulfilling their desires. Additionally, we plan to be an inclusive business by employing people with disabilities and individuals from disadvantaged groups. We also intend to expand our services to include health and wellbeing education.

FOUNDER **Dominika Bohovicova**

“The incubation program helped me look at my business plan with a realistic perspective and hear opinions from more experienced people. It gave me the opportunity to learn how to get things right in business and to recognize the importance of things I had previously overlooked.”

bohovicovadominika@gmail.com

Dizajn pre zmenu Slovensko

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The purpose is to support the creative process of working with children, inspired by the design thinking method. Our target group are teachers, children, young people, students

FOUNDERS Henrieta Gergelová
Vanesa Kováčová

“The incubation program helped us with mental support and reinforcement that truly make a difference.”

henrieta.gubanova@gmail.com

Nitrianske V.I.P.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

SAGGIO is a project of the civic association Nitrianske V.I.P, o.z. We are a community of people dedicated to volunteering and helping those in need. The main goal of the SAGGIO project is to operate a safe space called the SAGGIO PARENTS CLUB, which will serve parents and foster parents of children with specific needs. The aim is to create a place where parents can work, relax, and socialize while their children receive professional care. The facility includes a work area, a social area with a café, a relaxation area with services, and a space for developmental activities.

FOUNDER **Ingrid Velčická**

“The program definitely provided a new outlook on the business, moved me further towards my goal, and helped build the profile of our program.”

oz@nrvip.sk

We Live

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Our platform encompasses a web interface, mobile application, and support centers, dedicated to cancer prevention for clients, employees, and patients. It focuses on promoting prevention awareness, healthy diet and exercise practices, insurance guidance, psychological support, social security, and information about treatment options. Our mission is to address the challenges faced by both patients and healthy individuals in coping with cancer. We aim to raise societal awareness about our collective responsibility towards our health and well-being.

FOUNDER **Viliam Gabria**

“During the program, I acquired skills such as establishing cooperation with suppliers and customers, navigating marketing strategies, and determining how and where to secure financing.”

viliam@welve.sk
www.welve.sk

Pretvory

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Europe and Slovakia are facing a problem with textile waste. I want to educate children, young people, and the public on how to reduce textile waste. My goal is to create an educational and co-design textile center where prototypes of recycled textile products and art pieces would be made, services for the public would be offered, and a "Do It Yourself" workshop would be available.

FOUNDER **Marcela Chreneková**

The program provided me with valuable knowledge and tools in strategic planning, marketing, and financial management. With the support and mentoring from experts, I gained the confidence and skills to effectively lead my business.

m.chrenekova@gmail.com

Riga

FOUNDER **Ineta Ozola**

“My experience with the incubation program was both inspiring and creatively enriching. It provided me with profound insights into entrepreneurship and helped me develop crucial skills for my idea.”

Instagram:
[@spekozolu_garsvielas](#)

Spēkozolu garšvielas

ABOUT THE PROJECT

My business idea involves offering natural, additive-free spices enhanced with herbs, weeds, and wild berries. Our products stand out for their high quality and unique health-promoting properties. We are committed to delivering a taste experience that is not only exceptional but also beneficial to our customers' health.

FOUNDER **Aija Cunska**

“The program helped me to identify the customer segment, establish pricing, assess business viability, and forecast finances.”

cunska.aija@gmail.com

SIA “ACR4edu”

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The business idea originated from a research project that identified issues in mathematics learning both in Latvia and globally. It emphasized the conditions and technologies capable of enhancing and expediting mathematics learning by fostering motivation, interest, and active participation. Currently, the product is undergoing prototype testing. It comprises an app designed for generating mathematical expressions and consolidating results, alongside a pressure-sensitive sensor pad facilitating immediate access to solutions. The technology's objective is to stimulate emotions through movement among children aged 3 to 13, thereby fostering increased interest in mathematics and encouraging engagement.

FOUNDER Rudīte Truce

"In-Habit, I would like to extend a heartfelt thank you for the following: - providing an excellent mentor and a responsive, highly professional Co-mentor; fostering the development of sales, social media, startup, and email marketing skills; enhancing our marketing strategy."

rudite@power-journey.com

Dzīvesveida un Labsajūtas tūrisma aģentūra Power Journey

ABOUT THE PROJECT

We offer workshop sessions for developing well-being habits, pilates health exercises, and hiking/well-being adventures incorporating elements of forest therapy. Our industry focuses on Health, with a sub-specialty in Well-being. While the well-being sector is a recent innovation in Latvia according to statistics, it has already become a hot topic in European countries and beyond, attracting attention from both companies and individuals.

FOUNDER **Madara Trupovniece**

"I learned financial planning skills and how to think 'outside the box'. For example, I learned to analyze exactly what the consumer wants to buy and how they want to feel, which was an unprecedented approach."

info.forestbee@gmail.com

Tūju stādaudzētava ar parku

ABOUT THE PROJECT

"Tūju stādaudzētava ar parku" offers a unique and relaxing experience through park visits and the organization of various events specifically tailored for families with children. This combination of serene park environments and engaging activities ensures a memorable experience for all visitors, providing both relaxation and entertainment.

FOUNDER **Jana Briede**

“The program helped me develop new skills, enhance market awareness, receive mentoring support, and gain industry knowledge.”

jana@jbconsulting.lv

SIA JB Consulting

ABOUT THE PROJECT

An innovative solution empowering startups through advanced stress measurement tools and resilience-building capabilities. We're not just a tech provider; we're strategic partners committed to fostering a robust, innovative ecosystem. Our platform promises not only enhanced well-being and productivity for startups but also offers VCs the opportunity to be part of a scalable, impactful venture with significant growth potential and attractive returns. Join us in shaping a healthier, more resilient startup landscape.

FOUNDERS **Mārtiņš Veide**
Edmunds Ābelītis
Dairis Lācis

“The program helped us gain a broader perspective on business, including insights into areas for expansion and opportunities for improvement.”

dzho@inbox.lv

ARsport SIA

ABOUT THE PROJECT

XRsport - Digital technology sports entertainment (AR + VR). We make physical activity fun using the latest digital technologies. Our offerings are suitable for a wide age group and are also available for companies (for team introductions and team building), schools (to learn about technology), and other interested parties.

FOUNDER **Karīna Volbeta**

“Through the program, I acquired skills such as collaboration, planning, project management, and social media marketing.”

k.volbeta@gmail.com

Colourable wallpapers “Little Dill & John”

ABOUT THE PROJECT

I offer wallpapers for children's rooms. Each wallpaper pattern is a visual story that can be followed, colored in, and added to. Our target audience are families with children and interior designers.

FOUNDERS Jūlija Pehtereva

Jevgēņijs Haustovs

“Now, the entire company structure is logically organized. We have defined new customer segments and targeted a new market, supported by comprehensive statistics. This process has enabled us to compile structured information for ourselves, investors, and partners.”

julia@te-d.com

TE-D

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Tara Energy Drink, or TE-D, specializes in producing 100% natural and sustainable drink kits, offering high-quality everyday beverages that benefit both you and the world. The greatest value of our product lies in its ability to completely replace all your tonic drinks for 30 days. Our primary objective is to enhance the quality of life for our customers.

FOUNDER **Miks Zvejnieks**

“The incubation program helped me to define the core business of the company, identify the target audience, and gain a comprehensive understanding of the business principles.”

miks.zvejnieks@gmail.com

Mindfield Sports

ABOUT THE PROJECT

We aim to create a sports development platform where athletes can maximize their potential. The platform will assess the athlete's physical and psychological performance status using a specific methodology. With the involvement of qualified specialists/mentors, it will then propose a tailored pathway to enhance performance and athletic potential.

FOUNDER **Baiba Ābelniece**

“The incubation program helped me to develop the skill to think like an entrepreneur and as well collaboration, planning, marketing.”

Baiba@finalmente.lv
www.finalmente.lv

Finalmente

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Finalmente organises active trips, events and creates exciting adventures.

FOUNDER **Anda Kiršteine**

“I got more specific about my business idea, started to develop a marketing strategy. I learnt some technical stuff and social networks. I am very happy with my mentors and the knowledge I gained from the programme! Thank you very much!”

managramatvedesia@inbox.lv

SIA Mana grāmatvede

ABOUT THE PROJECT

I provide online training for self-employed and self-employed individuals on accounting.

FOUNDER Artūrs Muskars

“The Program helped me to set up my own business. More than the programme itself, which makes you think about your idea. Introduced to a mentor who gave a good support in this experience. I developed networking, financial planning.”

rullejums@gmail.com

Instagram: [@rullejums.saldejums](https://www.instagram.com/rullejums.saldejums)

Rullējums

ABOUT THE PROJECT

“Rullējums” is an ice cream with a unique way of preparation. The ice cream is made in front of the customer, using fresh ingredients of their choice and a cold ice cream base.

FOUNDER **Evija Nete**

“It has helped me a lot to understand both the customer segment and the direction I want to go in, and has increased my understanding of the company's needs. And it has given me the motivation to move towards my goal.”

evijanete@gmail.com

Cietais losjona gabaliņš

ABOUT THE PROJECT

I create sustainable, environmentally and people-friendly cosmetics - solid lotion bars. The solid lotion piece is produced using 100% natural ingredients and sustainable packaging. The aim is to minimise the negative impact on human health and the environment.

FOUNDER **Aija Murde**

“The IN-HABIT incubation programme helped me to develop new skills, create a marketing strategy, identify customer segments and raise awareness of the company's needs.”

forestprana@gmail.com

<https://www.facebook.com/forestprana/>

Forest Prana

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Our business draws on ancestral wisdom and modern science to offer people natural and effective health products. Our main product is handmade oxymels - traditional medicinal elixirs made from honey, vinegar and herbs grown in our rich, ecological natural environment. Our aim is to help people live healthier, happier and more in harmony with nature. Oxymels will give you a natural and effective way to take care of your health, using the wisdom of our ancestors and the advances of modern science.

FOUNDER **Vineta Domaševiča**

“The IN-HABIT incubation programme helped me to raise awareness of the company's needs.”

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<https://estetiska-mikropigmentacija.lv>

ESTETIK CARE

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Aesthetic and Medical Micropigmentation. My goal is to help people recover and improve their appearance not only physically but also morally. Especially after operations treating scars or other pigmentation issues.

I believe that micropigmentation, medical cosmetology and dermapigmentation can combine skin health and aesthetic pleasure in a way that promotes self-confidence and self-fulfilment.

FOUNDER **Aleksandra Baltā**

“Understand how I can reach and find my customer. Develop a sales plan and set a clear vision. Negotiation, collaboration, planning. Project management and everything that was included in the program was very helpful.”

https://www.instagram.com/big_smalltalk_lv/?igsh=NGYxNGljMXhIN3M0

Big small talk

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Small TALK is my organisation, which refers to the part of education that changes the approach to communication for clients (children and adults) with the philosophical method and extends the impact of the role of interest education, e.g. emphasising good performance and effective soft skills such as reasoning, multiple interpretation, problematisation and conceptualisation. Philosophy is a practice, not just the study of the ready-made ideas of other greats. By philosophising, better results can be achieved in education and in the personal development of each individual.

FOUNDER **Māra Vilciņa**

“The IN-HABIT incubation programme helped me to create a business strategy, understand more about the customer, create a sales strategy and become more proactive.”

sustaineventslatvia@gmail.com

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/sustain-events-latvia>

Sustain Events Latvia

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Seminars, meetings and other business events can be organised according to the principles of the circular economy, i.e. planning the waste stream, reducing transport, choosing locally produced products, more environmentally friendly decorations and entertainment, services and materials.

FOUNDER **Signe Turauska**

“The IN-HABIT incubation programme helped me to develop new skills such as leadership, information seeking, financial planning.”

www.dabaslaboratorija.lv

FB, IG: dabaslaboratorija

Dabas laboratorija

ABOUT THE PROJECT

The “Dabas laboratorija” produces high-quality cold-pressed juices and shots, as well as other herbal products. These juices can be called living because they are not pasteurised or subjected to any additional processing, thus preserving the vitamins and minerals as much as possible. The juices are bottled in 300ml bottles, where more than half a kilo of fruit, berries, vegetables and herbs are used to produce each bottle of juice. Juices are like the best “fast food” for the body, absorbed in a few minutes to provide quick, natural energy in the longest form.

FOUNDER **Agnese Straume-Apsīte**

“The IN-HABIT incubation programme helped me to define the idea and believe in it more.”

straume.agnese@gmail.com

Whispers of Generations

ABOUT THE PROJECT

A design exercise book that captures memories, sparks conversations and bridges the gap between generations.

Gracias!
Grazie!
Ďakujeme!
Paldies!

